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Foucauldian Power Relations in Ishiguro's *The Remains of the Day*

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ABSTRACT:

By tracing the reaction of the protagonist and foil and the concerning power structures in *The Remains of the Day* by Kazuo Ishiguro, this study deals with resistance in the personal and social sphere through the traditional action-oriented approach. *The Remains of the Day* narrates an old waiter's life-long memories during his service. Regardful to the values of his profession, the protagonist accepts the patterns of the ideal leader and remains in the current traditional power structure deridingly—even after he realizes his mistake. Considering Michel Foucault's definition of outgrowing resistance, the housekeeper, on the other hand, ceases the existing traditional power structure in English society in the years leading up to the Second World War. The housekeeper's method of independence goes through the steps proposed by Foucault for the moral formation of individuality. She leaves the traditional power structure for the sake of society's modern power understanding. For Foucault, power consists of the multiplicity of relations of forces that flow affectionally in the most delicate mechanisms of social interaction. Foucauldian modern power study discusses the politically controlling process in individual relationships and social layers. Impossible to get out of the power relations, resistance against it is inevitable from within the power structure, and Ishiguro's novel is a paragon for such an expressive function.

Introduction

The intellectual and cultural transformation of the socio-political system in modernity caused humans to question liberation in the context of existence principally. The blurred transparency of modernization increased the extent of ambiguity, confusion, dispersion, conflicts, and loneliness; thereby, humanity's captivity was promised in the torus of the concerns of power, industry, and technology. The consequences of modernization affected social life by redefinition of identities and beliefs, assimilation, homogenization, and systematic power domination. By interaction between the novel and philosophy, coding philosophical mysteries of the novels of the 20th century—against the legacy of the 19th century—existence and the comprehensiveness of power relations are underlined as the focal point. The concept of power is a fundamental issue discussed invariably, and Foucault addressed it by highlighting oppression through coercive power to notify the resistance of the oppressed. Paul Michel Foucault (1926-1984) was a French philosopher, historian, and poststructuralist theorist of the 20th century who debated society, politics, and history; he studied the mechanisms of power and hegemony to

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monitor human captivity after modernity in the philosophical, literary, sociological, and political spheres.

Power was always identified as abstract, flexible, and dynamic than any form of domination. For Bertrand Russell, unlike Marx, the origin of power is economic and military force, a dynamic phenomenon mered from any limited wealth, economy, military, and political propaganda. Thus, power is not limited to structures, but its traces are a part of a whole. (Russel 5) According to Foucault, the modern definition of power is the ontology against customary sovereignty. (During 130) Foucault retreats from traditional power realization and examines its common functioning among the members/institutions of society (Mills 33) as an executive strategy—not an implement to acquire:

One doesn't have here a power which is wholly in the hands of one person who can exercise it alone and totally over the others. It's a machine in which everyone is caught, those who exercise power just as much as those over whom it is exercised.... Power...becomes a machinery that no one owns. Certainly everyone doesn't occupy the same position; certain positions preponderate and permit an effect of supremacy to be produced. This is so much the case that class domination can be exercised just to the extent that power is dissociated from individual might. (Foucault[e] 156).

Power stabilizes, restores, and improves itself through transformation by expanding its network in institutions, media, beliefs, and relationships. For Foucault, power is a process, strategy, and set of movements that affect other possible actions. Modern power, its extent, expansion, and reproduction methods are fundamentally distinct from traditional understanding manifested in its displayed hegemony. This contemporary power is invisible, and its authority lies in its inconspicuousness. In consort with all functions, modernity failed to provide clarity under the rule of reason, excellence, and human liberation: technology changed into a mass destructive element during WWI and WW2, and the emergence of identity issues, alienation, and cultural ambiguity caused modern people to suspect the foundations of modernity, technology, and scientism as the utter regulation of reason.

The new structure of power after the birth of the modern era is rooted in the fabric of society, rotating people through normality. Society defines normality by science and social habits, dividing people into conventional and unconventional groups. Social behaviors are constantly monitored as normal, and according to Foucault, power exists in all social relations: “Power with a capital P, dominating and imposing its rationality upon the totality of the social body....power relations...are multiple; they have different forms, they can be in play in family relations, or within an institution, or an administration” (Foucault[a] 38). Therefore, all relationships between people are based on power, and a flexible power hierarchy is formed. (Mills 49) However, this hierarchy is constantly challenged, and Foucault emphasizes the challenge in which power flows beneath divisions, inequalities, and instability (Foucault[c] 94).

For Foucault, in the 16th and 17th centuries, the population increase in Europe created concerns for governments, which caused a new power mechanism in Europe. This mechanism of power was not aligned with the power of the authority but was more dependent on the people to efficiently exploit their labor power by debating “the problem of sovereignty (what is the sovereign? how is he constituted as sovereign? what bond of obedience ties individuals to the sovereign?)” (Foucault[e]187). This new power mechanism was formed by legislation under two poles: a) bio-power, which focuses on population control and management of lives and is concerned with regulating phenomena such as birth, death, disease, health, and sexual relations; b) knowledge-power; deals with the process of training people—through institutions, such as schools and hospitals (Rabinow 262-267).

Power also proceeds through the sovereignty’s functional violence in society for Foucault. Bio-power aims to pull lives, reform, and lodge the sustainability mechanism. Instead of fearful awe, such a power is measured, qualitative, and admirable (Foucault[c] 144-145). Foucault does not mean that the justice organization disappears in the context of power, but the laws become more normative and institutionalized in social institutions. Norms derive their worth by creating a negative standard. Therefore, the criteria that create knowledge-power become norms that people gage to verify. Thus, people self-imposedly desire the norms and voluntarily act passively. Certain methods in institutions create social norms, and the knowledge-power mechanism shapes modern institutions by educating people. Thus, power orders society by increasing the scope of power control over the people.

Foucault says, “Where there is a power, there is a resistance...this resistance is never in a position of exteriority in relation to power” (95). Thus, the people who are fighting for power are not only in a master-servant relationship. He presents a positive description of resistance against power by “the relation to oneself and care for the self as a site for resistance” (Hartmann 9). For Foucault, power structuration is “the way in which the conduct of individuals or of groups might be directed... to govern, in this sense, is to structure the possible field of action of others” (Foucault[d] 221). Foucault depicts power as operating through the space creation in which individuals can engage in possible behavior; instead of exerting external pressure, power works by guiding people’s behavior. Foucault “describes the nature of power as the modification of action by action; put somewhat differently, power is no longer conceived as the abstract relation of forces but as the structuring of the field of possible actions by means of action” (Hartman 9).

Foucault advocates conscious resistance to imposed social pressures to define individuality. Accepting the self that external deterrence imposes on people makes them unable to be pleased. Foucault’s first suggestion for resisting the normalizing effects of society is the denial of the normalized identity (the self) imposed on the individual. Freedom is rooted in personal realizations, but governing laws determine what is permissible and what is not, and for Foucault, ethics are methods in which people take shelter. By ethics, one finds a way of being

based on personal inspiration and critical thinking. Ethics re-examine the interactions of individuals to preserve intimate freedom.

For Foucault, three factors influence ethical self-formation: a) Appropriate Space: The space that encourages people to undertake different selves. The structure of ethical self-formation requires an experiential environment where people participate in the production of their cutting line. This is “the type of safe, experimental environment where individuals can participate in the ongoing production of themselves with and in front of others and where they can be both witness to and resource for the experiments of other selves” (Infinito 168). b). Curriculum as Genealogy: By “an understanding of the discursive elements of culture and of our identity” (Infinito 168), Foucault believes that people can accept their reality and change it at the same time. Humanity should not miss the opportunities to create change; a person should evaluate a situation with hope and a correct understanding of the past and present and gain the motivation to make a change. “Foucault maintained that seeing the world we inhabit [including our own identity] as the product of contingent, arbitrary, ‘man-made’ games of truth allows us a more useful understanding of our past and of our present situation” (Infinito 169) c). The Attitude of Critique: Human’s critical receptive is an essence of change. It is “a willingness to hold in one thought both the reality of the present (and ourselves) gleaned by revealing the events that preceded and shaped it and the idea or practice of ourselves as an object of purposeful elaboration” (Infinito 170).

Power Relations in *The Remains of the Day*

Japanese descendant Kazuo Ishiguro (1954-) immigrated to England during childhood and graduated with a degree in creative writing. The setting of his novels is the period of WWI and WWII. The narrator of *The Remains of the Day*—a Booker Prize-winning novel in 1989—is Stevens, a butler. Stevens’s life at Darlington Hall moves on among the Nazis and the English noblemen and continues in the years between WWI and WWII and thereafter. *The Remains of the Day* is not a historical novel but a narration of experiences that profile the narrator’s personality. Stevens has served in Darlington Hall for Lord Darlington for over thirty years and later for the new master, an American businessman, Mr. Farraday. He sets off for a trip to the West Country, where he meets his former colleague, who got married but, in a letter, informs Stevens that she has left her husband. During the journey, reminiscent of their past, Stevens hopes to persuade her to return to Darlington Hall.

Foucault discusses normality, abnormality, and normalization and genealogy of the norm “to identify an historical phenomenon... of a longstanding technique of power” (Kelly 4). Norms in the classical British Culture were formed to serve the nobility, fulfill their service expectations in the realm of obedience and self-forgetfulness, and control sexual and emotional instincts (Tamaya 5). Since the English butler is chief of the housekeepers and is in contact with the master and guests, his behavior, appearance, and even accent are of particular importance,

and he is obliged to follow the predetermined patterns. Stevens brands the butler's self-discipline as "dignity"; the quality of service is a professional duty that depends on the individual's "dignity":

'dignity' has to do crucially with a butler's ability not to abandon the professional being he inhabits.... The great butlers are great by virtue of their ability to inhabit their professional role and inhabit it to the utmost.... They wear their professionalism as a decent gentleman will wear his suit t: he will not let ruffians or circumstance tear it off him in the public gaze; he will discard it when, and only when, he wills to do so, and this will invariably be when he is entirely alone. It is, as I say, a matter of 'dignity'. (Ishiguro 43-44)

Stevens follows Lord Darlington's perception of society and manages the crew and their duties in meetings at Darlington Hall. Stevens controls his emotions; marriage is unprofessional to him, and he never expresses his love for a woman: "In his relationship with Miss Kenton, Stevens prevented his professional relationship from deviating from the proper basis and therefore ruled out the possibility of romance between them" (Foniokova 95). Stevens' father is a butler in Darlington Hall, and when he dies, Stevens is busy serving guests and says: "I'm very busy just now....please don't think me unduly improper in not ascending to see my father in his deceased condition just at this moment. You see, I know my father would have wished me to carry on just now" (Ishiguro 111). Controlling his emotions as a British cultural norm looks obligatory for butlers: "I believe, a quality that will mark out the English landscape to any objective observer as the most deeply satisfying in the world, and this quality is probably best summed up by the term 'greatness'" (Ishiguro 28). Due to Stevens' obedience, he and Lord Darlington's views on various issues, including political issues, get on the same page. Before the beginning of WWII and after WWI, Stevens is aware of his master's role in political decisions—including millions of deaths in Europe—citing that Lord Darlington is an aristocrat with opinions unquestionable:

[An] idealistic generation for whom the question was not simply one of how well one practised one's skills, but to what end one did so; each of us harboured the desire to make our own small contribution to the creation of a better world, and saw that, as professionals, the surest means of doing so would be to serve the great gentlemen of our times in whose hands civilization had been entrusted. (Ishiguro 122)

A butler must be reliable, witnesses secrets, and is always ready to serve the master; Lord Darlington guarantees Stevens' loyalty and says: "Oh, that's all right. You can say anything in front of Stevens, I can assure' you.'" (Ishiguro 77). He is also rapid and strong in transition and understands every hint like an invisible contractor. Stevens struggles "to achieve that balance between attentiveness and the illusion of absence that is essential to good waiting" (Ishiguro 75). He has internalized all the norms related to being a good butler and does not show any resistance

to the power source in Darlington House. For Foucault, resistance requires the moral formation of individuality. The environment that allows a person to test different selves and situations is the first determinant in the moral formation of individuality. Power is exercised by individuals, who are “objects and... instruments of its exercise” (Foucault[b] 170). Power is spread “between different individuals and groups and only exists when it is being exercised” (O’Farrell 99). In Darlington Hall, power produces Stevens’s reality and identity; it “create[s] certain kinds of individuals” (Taylor 166).

In Darlington Hall—a cold and dark place that, for Miss Kenton, is reminiscent of a cell in a prison—the interest to Miss Kenton is a test. She guides Stevens toward the light and informs Stevens about other possible situations. The butler’s room causes restricted activities, leaving him no private life. As Miss Kenton says, “[This] room resembles a prison cell. All one needs is a small bed in the corner, and one could well imagine condemned men spending their last hours here” (Ishiguro 174). Here, every butler is monitored to ensure they keep their duties efficiently. Thus, “segmentation consolidates order and supervision, ensuring that the butlers only engage in organized and approved activities. In the panopticon, each convict lives in an enclosed, segmented cell; the slightest movement is supervised; and all events are recorded” (Zhen 47). This is similar to Foucault’s definition of power relations:

Induce in the inmate a state of conscious and permanent visibility that assures the automatic functioning of power. So to arrange things that the surveillance is permanent in its effects, even if it is discontinuous in its action; that the perfection of power should tend to render its actual exercise unnecessary; that this architectural apparatus should be a machine for creating and sustaining a power relation independent of a person who exercises it (Foucault[b] 201).

Miss Kenton tentatively asks Stevens about his plans and comments: “[It] occurs to me that you must be a well-contented man.... I really cannot imagine what more you might wish for in life” (Ishiguro 182). However, Stevens rationalizes his profession as a butler who devoted his life to his profession and does not share his emotions. After the death of Stevens’ father, Miss Kenton tries to inform Stevens about his likely fate. After all, Stevens becomes aware of his mistakes and sobs instinctively when a retired lackey suggests: “You’ve got to enjoy yourself. The evening’s the best part of the day. You’ve done your day’s work. Now you can put your feet up and enjoy it. That’s how I look at it. Ask anybody, they’ll all tell you” (Ishiguro 256). The departure at the end of the trip is another prospect for Stevens to take advantage of an alternative life.

The second determining element in character analysis is to obtain sufficient information about the current cultural, historical, and social marvel. After WWII, due to the extra taxes imposed by the government on aristocratic mansions, owners had to change them into public museums or sell them to mostly affluent American businessmen. Eventually, butlers leave

their profession; in the novel, this is proven by the reduction of the number of employees at Darlington Hall and Mr. Benn's leaving the position. However, Stevens insists on his career and, ignorant of the facts, shows no interest in accepting Lord Darlington as an English lord who eases relations between Britain and Germany. Still, Stevens is pleased only because his master is an aristocrat, without thinking of his position after Lord Darlington's death. He stumbles due to the burden of duties, introduces his new master as an American gentleman, and the reader realizes he is close to his father's tragic end. Thus, "Stevens' attitude to his father was consistent with his reliance on an anachronistic social order to provide him with a sense of self-definition" (O'Brien 806).

Stevens' lack of knowledge of his situation prevents him from forming his individuality, a critical spirit against the existing situation. When following the order to fire two servants for being Jewish, Miss Kenton asks him to protest the decision: "Does it not occur to you, Mr. Stevens, that to dismiss Ruth and Sarah on these grounds would be simply wrong? I will not stand for such things. "I will not work in a house in which such things can occur" (Ishiguro 157); Stevens responds: "I will ask you not to excite yourself and to conduct yourself in a manner befitting your position. This is a very straightforward matter. If his lordship wishes...to be discontinued, then there is little more to be said" (Ishiguro 157). According to Stevens, loyalty to the master is part of a butler's profession; it is more important than having personal opinions and a critical view of the other issues:

It is not simply that one is unlikely to be able to meet the many demands of service at the higher levels while one's attentions are being diverted by such matters; more fundamentally, a butler who is forever attempting to formulate his own 'strong opinions' on his employer's affairs is bound to lack one quality essential in all good professionals: namely, loyalty. (Ishiguro 210).

Stevens, the narrator, portrays Miss Kenton as threatening and encouraging; he hears "the sound of angry footsteps rattling the floorboards" and Miss Kenton "glaring up" angrily at Stevens "from the foot of the stairs" (Ishiguro 226); but then, she beckons Stevens to come out of the room to the bliss of new experiences. Formerly, Miss Kenton lived with her aunt in Darlington Hall, but feeling emptiness made her find a job she succeeded in. However, against Stevens, she puts her personal dreams ahead of her professional dreams and leaves Darlington Hall and even her husband three times. However, when she meets Stevens after years, she says:

'What a terrible mistake I've made with my life.' And you get to thinking about a different life, a better life you might have had. For instance, I get to thinking about a life I may have had with you, Mr Stevens. And I suppose that's when I get angry over some trivial little thing and leave. But each time I do so, I realize before long - my rightful place is with my husband. After all, there's no turning back the clock now. One can't be

forever dwelling on what might have been. One should realize one has as good as most, perhaps better, and be grateful. (Ishiguro 251)

When Miss Kenton is unsatisfied with her life, she changes it due to her circumstances. Her decision to marry and leave Darlington Hall shows her awareness of being an independent woman. Stevens, the narrator, never reveals Miss Kenton's political perspective. However, her reaction to the dismissal of the Jewish butlers shows that she was not aligned with the political inclinations of her master, and any social position does not make her adopt power. She criticizes the decisions and does not shy away from expressing her opinions. She shows her anger with her heavy steps and frowning sight, as well as demonstrating her love by bringing a bouquet of flowers to Stevens. Later, Lord Darlington realizes his mistake of firing the Jewish butlers, and Stevens conveys it to Miss Kenton: "What's done can hardly be undone. But it is at least a great comfort to hear his lordship declare so unequivocally that it was all a terrible misunderstanding.... I recall you were as distressed by the episode as I was" (Ishiguro 161). However, Miss Kenton responds: "As I recall, you thought it was only right and proper that Ruth and Sarah be sent packing. You were positively cheerful about it.... Why, Mr Stevens, why, why, why do you always have to pretend?" (Ishiguro 162).

Stevens institutionalized professionalism unconsciously, and it is impossible for him to distinguish personal opinions from those of his master. Due to his loyalty, he cannot achieve his dream of being ideal. Stevens finally drowned in a "deepened understanding of the social realm that has escaped him... within the suffocating routine which had been his life" (Penner 29). This awareness makes Stevens "the surroundings grew unrecognizable" for him, and eventually, "[he] had gone beyond all previous boundaries" (Ishiguro 24). After the end of WWII, Lord Darlington is put on trial as a traitor, and during the last trip, even Stevens denies his service to Lord Darlington.

Conclusion

In *The Remains of the Day*, Ishiguro portrays two completely different characters: Stevens, the narrator, is a passive person, and Miss Kenton reacts due to the pace of life. As a butler, Stevens normalized his acts by the stereotypes of being an ideal housekeeper, sensitive to his position while serving his master and guests. Careful at every moment, Stevens has dignity in his burdens; he does not strive for privacy to not deviate from the traditional power structure of Darlington Hall. After all, he realizes his faults but returns to Darlington Hall and practices being humorous just because the American master finds wit as the code of human fondness. Stevens remains in the traditional power structure and does not represent Foucault's relation to any type of resistance.

However, Miss Kenton leaves the traditional power structure in Darlington Hall and realizes her occupation as a reason for independence and self-otherness. She is an expert but denies its

regularizing effects and goes through the stages proposed by Foucault for the moral formation of individuality. Decisively, she declares her satisfaction with the expectations that will be formed after her husband's retirement and the birth of her grandson. According to the definitions of the power structure in society, Miss Kenton has chosen the greatest pick and broke out of the traditional power structure in Darlington Hall; she even left her husband many times, although it is impossible to escape the modern power edifice in society. In Foucault's method of resistance, which takes place from within power, a person can only show resistance in the space that the power structure allows; therefore, the method proposed by Foucault does not lead to the entire freedom—as Miss Kenton, who is not fully satisfied with her life.

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